

THE ROLE OF THE ECONOMY IN THE EFFECTIVE USE OF TOURISM AND CULTURAL HERITAGE FACILITIES

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Abstract. This article analyzes the importance of the development of the tourism industry in the socio-economic life of the country, the measures taken in modernizing the industry and gives conclusions and suggestions by the author.

Key words: tourism, economic situation, infrastructure, guide, excursion, travel, historical monuments, investments, hotel, tourist services.

Introduction. In scientific research devoted to the emergence of objects of ancient cultural heritage on a global scale, the development of evolution, the preservation of the urban planning system, the restoration and repair of archaeological and architectural monuments, it is important to improve ways to preserve historical monuments in their original state, and effectively use historical monuments to increase tourism potential. In these studies, the determination of the specific historical and architectural features of architectural monuments, the further increase of tourist opportunities of historical regions, the effective use of objects of cultural heritage are among the urgent tasks. In our country, in recent years, the emphasis on national values, material and cultural monuments has changed radically. In particular, monuments of architecture and archeology, a more thorough study of cultural heritage, their effective use in the development of international and domestic tourism are rising to the level of state policy. "It is

necessary to preserve our cultural heritage, a masterpiece of our rich history, and to decorate it for future generations”¹.

Creating favorable conditions for the improvement of tourism, primarily in the private sector, increasing the competitiveness and quality of the services provided, actively and comprehensively promoting national tourism products on the world market, special attention was also paid to further strengthening foreign relations with the countries of Europe and Southeast Asia in order to radically improve the transport communication system in the Republic in order to increase turnover, the number of passengers transported and investments.

It should be noted that on October 4, 1993, Uzbekistan became the first member of the World Tourism Organization among Central Asian countries. This, in turn, gave a great positive impetus to the development of international tourism in Uzbekistan.

It is clear to all that the development of tourism in our republic has a huge economic effect, since it allows foreign currency to be imported (cotton, gas, oil) without releasing resources. Analysis shows that in most developed countries, income from tourism brings much more foreign exchange revenues than in other areas. For example: Turkey is 4-5 billion a year. if the dollar exports goods, 10 billion from tourism activities. earns more than dollars. We can see the same high rates in Austria, England, Italy, France, Spain.

Literature analysis. Currently, developed countries are conducting a number of research studies on the impact of tourism on their economy, social sphere, ecology and other spheres. The main content of these studies is whether the social capital is compatible with the policy in the direction of tourism.

¹ Appeal of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Supreme Assembly. 29.12.2020.

According to the results of this study, they are interrelated, because the growth of social capital has an indirect effect on the development of the tourism industry².

Kujel Yu. In his textbook, he revealed the role of tourism in the socio-economic development of the country. In this, it is necessary to pay special attention to tourism as the fastest growing sector of the country³.

According to Russian scientists N. Morozova and M. Morozov, the modern tourism industry has undergone great changes with the introduction of new computer technologies. It is practically impossible for any organization to operate successfully in the tourist business market without using modern information technology⁴.

N.Khaydarov believes that in the country it is necessary to sharply increase the intake of foreign students in the field of Education. They live like tourists for at least 4 years of study. The opportunity to come and go to see their parents and close friends during the period of their studies is very great⁵.

According to the reviewed experts, the development of the tourism industry has a direct impact on the development of all sectors of the country. Nowadays, it is necessary to show the tourism potential of our country to the world by using the existing tourism potential based on the experiences of developed countries.

Research methodology. In the course of the research, the best practices of foreign countries in the development of tourism were studied. Official tourism statistics were used. In the article, methods such as theoretical observation,

² Barnabé Walheer, Linjia Zhang . Profit Luenberger and Malmquist-Luenberger indexes for multi-activity decision-making units: The case of the star-rated hotel industry in China //International Journal of Tourism Management. Pages 1-604 (December 2018) pp.1-11.

³ Кужеля Ю. Л. Туризм и гостеприимство. Учебник:- М. : Издательство Юрайт, 2018. — 439 с.

⁴ Морозова Н., Морозов М., Информационное обеспечение туризма. Учебник.Москва, КноРус, 2016, 7 с.

⁵ N.Xaydarov. Turizmni rivojlantirishda xorijiy davlatlar tajribasi. Ochiq iqtisodiyot: sog'lom raqobat, biznes muhiti investision muhit jozibadorligi / xalqaro amaliy anjuman / TDIU

systematic approach, observation, generalization, comparative analysis, and synthesis were effectively used..

Research results. One of the important advantages of historical cultural tourism over other types of recreation is that it is in demand all year round, and its significant difference is that it is not seasonal. This tour is relevant at any time of the year, since tourists can take an excursion to visit museums, see historical monuments and sights of the country. The role of historical and archaeological objects that exist in the regions is important in the development of historical and cultural tourism. Their historicity, their place in the history of the region and the degree of preservation help to increase the number of tourists interested in it. For any visiting tourist, the presence of several objects in one location will extend the duration of his trip. This process gives the opportunity to export more tourist services and the development of related industries.

Speaking about the development of tourism infrastructure in Uzbekistan, it is important to dwell on the division of the country into the main tourism regions. Today, there are four main tourist regions in the Republic; they are tourism regions of Fergana, Samarkand-Bukhara, Tashkent and Khorezm. Organization of "Ancient Bukhara" and "Samarkand City" tourism zones in the cities of Bukhara and Samarkand, implementation of a total of about 450 projects, including restoration and conservation of 50 cultural heritage objects, construction and restoration of more than 50 hotels, 100 ha construction of a nearby catering facility is underway. The visa and registration process for foreign tourists has been simplified.

There are more than 7,300 objects of cultural heritage in our country, and nearly 200 of them are included in the UNESCO list. At the same time, it is possible to open new tourist destinations using the opportunities of our country's unique nature and beautiful resorts. Actively involving world brands in this field, we need to pay special attention to the development of pilgrimage tourism,

ecological, educational, ethnographic, gastronomic tourism and other branches of this field.

In the economic approach, tourism is defined as a unique sector that includes the activities of historical, cultural, recreational and other organizations, which include the production of complex services and products, and the introduction of targeted investments. As an economic phenomenon, tourism is of great importance in terms of its impact on the regional economy, as well as its dependence on it at the same time. Given the high potential for the development of historical and cultural tourism in our country, it is possible to note the positive and negative effects of tourism on the economy based on data analysis of economic literature:

- increased employment rates due to increased employment. In developed countries, 3-5% of jobs belong to the tourism industry;
- tourism indirectly affects the development of other sectors in the process of its development (construction, transport, Road, Food Trade Industry, etc.;
- the tourism industry has a high growth rate, with foreign exchange revenues from tourism in countries around the world increasing by an average of 8-12% each year in the preceding pandemic crisis;
- the "multiplying effect" of tourism, that is, the high turnover of funds spent on tourism;
 - ensures structural changes in the national economy;
 - attract foreign investment and bring income in foreign currency;
 - improves the economic and social image of the country in foreign countries;
 - encourages the creation and development of national parks and reserves;
 - serves to preserve works of art and traditions, etc.

It is also necessary to cite some negative factors that affect the development of historical and cultural tourism. In particular, the preservation, reconstruction of

historical and cultural objects requires significant investments. Some developing countries may not be able to allocate sufficient funds to sustain them due to capital shortages. The development of the industry directly depends on the state policy. The rational policy of the state leads to the development of the field of historical and cultural tourism, the strengthening of international cooperation, the effective use of innovations and information technologies in the field, and on the contrary, the unreasonable policy leads to the neglect of tourism objects and monuments, and to looting.

Through its participation in the processes of the international tourism market, the country ensures the inflow of foreign currency and leads to the improvement of the state of the balance of payments. The generation of income by international tourism also affects investments in other sectors of the economy. This leads to economic growth and development through a multiplier effect. Thus, in addition to the development of production, the country improves its infrastructure and transport, communication lines, trade relations, etc., which ultimately leads to the restructuring of the economic system.

Conclusions and suggestions. As a result of the theoretical and practical study of improving the economic efficiency of the industry, the following conclusions were drawn and recommendations were developed:

- to improve quality and exemplary service to museums and cultural heritage objects and thereby strengthen their reputation;
- organization of cultural events such as international exhibitions, conferences, festivals to present the historical heritage of the country in the world tourist market;
- by significantly increasing the role of archaeological monuments in the field of historical and cultural tourism, bringing them to the brand level among foreign and local tourists;
- partial (conservation and restoration) preparation of archaeological

monuments for museum exhibition;

- to introduce the traditions of national crafts to the world by establishing the organization of master classes in folk art centers for tourists.

In general, national tourism will become one of the most profitable sectors of our country in the future. For this, all opportunities, political peace and, most importantly, the humanity and hospitality of our people serve as extremely important factors in our country..

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